

Strong antidistinguishability does not imply maximal contextuality

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Abstract

A measurement outcome that has zero probability for a quantum state gives evidence that the system was not prepared in that state. Antidistinguishability formalizes this viewpoint, while contextuality asks whether the constraints imposed by compatible measurements can be explained by noncontextual value assignments. Srikumar et al. introduced a notion of contextuality for finite sets of pure quantum states and proved that maximal contextuality implies strong antidistinguishability. This result suggests a close connection between the geometry of state exclusion and the minimal contextual resources contained in a finite family of states. They conjectured the converse, namely that every strongly antidistinguishable non-orthogonal set of pure states is maximally contextual. We give a counterexample in the four-dimensional Hilbert space \mathbb{C}^4 . Our construction shows that the implication from maximal contextuality to strong antidistinguishability is strictly one-way, and that maximal contextuality requires a minimality condition not captured by strong antidistinguishability alone.

1 Introduction

Quantum theory departs from classical intuition not only through probabilities, but also through impossibilities. When a measurement outcome has probability zero for a given pure state, observing that outcome lets us say with certainty that the system was not prepared in that state [1, 2]. Thus, the geometry of Hilbert space turns orthogonality into a form of logical evidence, since some outcomes do not identify the state but can still rule states out.

A standard way to formalize this concept is through antidistinguishability [3–9]. A set of pure states is weakly antidistinguishable when there is a projective measurement such that every outcome excludes at least one state in the set [10]. It is strongly antidistinguishable when, in addition, each state has an outcome that excludes that state and no other member of the set. These conditions are important because they connect state exclusion to contextuality [11].

Srikumar et al. established a precise link between these ideas [12]. In particular, weak antidistinguishability is enough to obtain the relevant contextual instance for a finite non-orthogonal set of pure states. They also proved that every maximally contextual such set must be strongly antidistinguishable. They conjectured that the converse also holds (see Figure 1). If a non-orthogonal finite set of pure states is strongly antidistinguishable, must it be maximally contextual? A positive answer would give a simple operational test for maximal contextuality, requiring only a projective measurement whose outcomes exclude the states one at a time.

We show that this converse is false. Our counterexample separates two notions that might otherwise appear to coincide. Consequently, the implication from maximal contextuality to strong

Figure 1: Hierarchy of the state-set properties considered in this work. For finite non-orthogonal families of pure states, contextuality is equivalent to weak antidistinguishability. Strong antidistinguishability is a stronger exclusion condition, while maximal contextuality requires contextuality with no contextual proper subset. The known implication from maximal contextuality to strong antidistinguishability is shown by the inner inclusion. The question mark indicates the conjectured converse, which is refuted by our counterexample.

antidistinguishability is strictly one-way. This clarifies the hierarchy between exclusion measurements and contextual resources, and shows that any characterization of maximal contextuality must include a genuine minimality requirement beyond strong antidistinguishability.

2 Preliminaries

Throughout this paper, \mathbb{C}^d denotes the d -dimensional complex vector space with inner product $\langle x, y \rangle = \sum_{r=1}^d \bar{x}_r y_r$.

A pure quantum state is represented by a unit vector $\psi \in \mathbb{C}^d$. For a unit vector ψ , the rank-one projector onto its span is

$$P_\psi = |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|.$$

2.1 Projective measurements and exclusion

Definition 1. A projection-valued measurement (PVM) on \mathbb{C}^d is a finite set $\{E_1, \dots, E_m\}$ of orthogonal projections satisfying

$$E_k^* = E_k, \quad E_k^2 = E_k, \quad E_k E_\ell = 0 \quad (k \neq \ell), \quad \sum_{k=1}^m E_k = I_d.$$

If q_1, \dots, q_d is an orthonormal basis, then

$$\{|q_1\rangle\langle q_1|, \dots, |q_d\rangle\langle q_d|\}$$

is a rank-one PVM.

Definition 2. Let ψ be a pure state and let E be a PVM outcome. We say that E excludes ψ if

$$E\psi = 0.$$

For a rank-one outcome $E = |q\rangle\langle q|$, this is equivalent to $\langle q, \psi \rangle = 0$.

Definition 3 (Weak and strong antidistinguishability). Let $S = \{\psi_1, \dots, \psi_n\}$ be a finite set of pure states.

- (a) S is weakly antidistinguishable if there is a PVM $\{E_1, \dots, E_m\}$ such that every outcome excludes at least one state in S . Equivalently, for every k there exists an index i with $E_k \psi_i = 0$.
- (b) S is strongly antidistinguishable if there is a PVM $\{E_1, \dots, E_m\}$ satisfying the weak condition and, in addition, for every state $\psi_i \in S$ there is an outcome $E_{k(i)}$ such that

$$E_{k(i)} \psi_i = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad E_{k(i)} \psi_j \neq 0 \quad \text{for every } j \neq i.$$

Such an outcome exclusively excludes ψ_i among the states in S .

2.2 Contextuality scenarios generated by a state set

Definition 4 (Context). A context in \mathbb{C}^d is a set of d rank-one projectors

$$\{|u_1\rangle\langle u_1|, \dots, |u_d\rangle\langle u_d|\}$$

where u_1, \dots, u_d is an orthonormal basis of \mathbb{C}^d .

Definition 5 (Generated contextuality scenario and contextual instance). Let T be a finite set of pure states in \mathbb{C}^d . A finite contextuality scenario generated by T is specified by a finite vertex set V of rank-one projectors with the following properties:

- V contains P_ψ for every $\psi \in T$;
- every projector in $V \setminus \{P_\psi : \psi \in T\}$ is orthogonal to at least one state in T .

The context set of the scenario, denoted $\mathcal{C}(V)$, is the set of all contexts whose projectors all lie in V . Thus, whenever an orthonormal basis of \mathbb{C}^d is represented inside V , that basis is one of the contexts of the scenario.

A value assignment on V is a function $v : V \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$. It is noncontextual for the scenario if every context $C \in \mathcal{C}(V)$ contains exactly one projector assigned value 1:

$$\sum_{P \in C} v(P) = 1.$$

The set T is a contextual instance of the generated scenario if there is no noncontextual value assignment satisfying

$$v(P_\psi) = 1 \quad \text{for every } \psi \in T.$$

The set T is called contextual if it is a contextual instance of at least one finite scenario generated by T .

Definition 6 (Maximal contextuality). A finite set S of pure states is maximally contextual if S is contextual and no proper subset $T \subsetneq S$ is contextual.

Theorem 1 ([12]). Let T be a finite non-orthogonal set of pure states in \mathbb{C}^d . Then T is weakly antidistinguishable if and only if T is contextual.

3 The counterexample mechanism

Proposition 1 (Inessential strongly antidistinguishable extensions). *Let x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4 be nonzero vectors in \mathbb{C}^4 , define*

$$\phi_i = \frac{x_i}{\|x_i\|} \quad (i = 1, 2, 3, 4),$$

and set

$$X = \{\phi_1, \phi_2, \phi_3, \phi_4\}, \quad Y = \{\phi_1, \phi_2, \phi_3\}.$$

Assume the following three conditions.

(i) *The four states in X are non-orthogonal.*

(ii) *There is an orthonormal basis f_1, f_2, f_3, f_4 of \mathbb{C}^4 such that*

$$\langle f_r, x_i \rangle = 0 \iff r = i \quad (1 \leq r, i \leq 4).$$

(iii) *There is an orthonormal basis q_1, q_2, q_3, q_4 of \mathbb{C}^4 such that*

$$\langle q_1, x_1 \rangle = 0, \quad \langle q_2, x_2 \rangle = 0, \quad \langle q_3, x_3 \rangle = 0, \quad \langle q_4, x_1 \rangle = 0.$$

Then X is strongly antidistinguishable, but X is not maximally contextual.

Proof. Condition (ii) implies

$$\langle f_r, \phi_i \rangle = 0 \iff r = i.$$

Hence the rank-one PVM

$$\mathcal{F} = \{|f_1\rangle\langle f_1|, |f_2\rangle\langle f_2|, |f_3\rangle\langle f_3|, |f_4\rangle\langle f_4|\}$$

strongly antidistinguishes X , since the outcome $|f_i\rangle\langle f_i|$ excludes ϕ_i and excludes no other member of X . In particular, X is weakly antidistinguishable. Since X is non-orthogonal, Theorem 1 implies that X is contextual.

Condition (iii) gives a different rank-one PVM,

$$\mathcal{Q} = \{|q_1\rangle\langle q_1|, |q_2\rangle\langle q_2|, |q_3\rangle\langle q_3|, |q_4\rangle\langle q_4|\}.$$

Its four outcomes exclude, respectively,

$$\phi_1, \quad \phi_2, \quad \phi_3, \quad \phi_1$$

among the states in Y . Thus every outcome of \mathcal{Q} excludes at least one state in Y , so Y is weakly antidistinguishable. Since Y is non-orthogonal, Theorem 1 implies that Y is contextual.

The set Y is a proper subset of X . Therefore X has a contextual proper subset, and so X is not maximally contextual. \square

Proposition 1 identifies the obstruction to the conjectured converse. A fourth state can be added to an already contextual triple in such a way that the enlarged quadruple has a perfectly diagonal certificate of strong antidistinguishability. The fourth state is then useful for producing the strong exclusion pattern, but it is not needed for contextuality.

Lemma 1 (Two-plane criterion for the subset measurement). *Let x_1, x_2, x_3 be nonzero vectors in \mathbb{C}^4 . Suppose there is a two-dimensional subspace $W \subset \mathbb{C}^4$ such that*

$$x_1 \in W,$$

and, writing Π_W for the orthogonal projection onto W ,

$$\Pi_W x_2 \neq 0, \quad \Pi_W x_3 \neq 0, \quad \langle \Pi_W x_2, \Pi_W x_3 \rangle = 0.$$

Then there is an orthonormal basis q_1, q_2, q_3, q_4 of \mathbb{C}^4 such that

$$\langle q_1, x_1 \rangle = 0, \quad \langle q_2, x_2 \rangle = 0, \quad \langle q_3, x_3 \rangle = 0, \quad \langle q_4, x_1 \rangle = 0.$$

Consequently, the normalized triple determined by x_1, x_2, x_3 is weakly antidistinguishable.

Proof. Set

$$u_2 = \Pi_W x_2, \quad u_3 = \Pi_W x_3.$$

By assumption, u_2 and u_3 are nonzero orthogonal vectors in the two-dimensional space W . Define

$$q_2 = \frac{u_3}{\|u_3\|}, \quad q_3 = \frac{u_2}{\|u_2\|}.$$

Then q_2, q_3 form an orthonormal basis of W . Moreover, since $q_2, q_3 \in W$,

$$\langle q_2, x_2 \rangle = \langle q_2, \Pi_W x_2 \rangle = \langle q_2, u_2 \rangle = 0,$$

and similarly

$$\langle q_3, x_3 \rangle = \langle q_3, \Pi_W x_3 \rangle = \langle q_3, u_3 \rangle = 0.$$

Choose any orthonormal basis q_1, q_4 of W^\perp . Since $x_1 \in W$, both q_1 and q_4 are orthogonal to x_1 . Hence q_1, q_2, q_3, q_4 is an orthonormal basis with the claimed exclusion pattern. \square

The repeated exclusion of one state in a weakly antidistinguishable triple has a simple geometric interpretation. The two outcomes excluding the same state span W^\perp , while the remaining two outcomes lie in a plane W containing that state. The other two states need only have orthogonal nonzero projections onto W .

4 An explicit construction

Figure 2 illustrates our construction. We work in \mathbb{C}^4 with the standard computational basis

$$e_1 = (1, 0, 0, 0)^T, \quad e_2 = (0, 1, 0, 0)^T, \quad e_3 = (0, 0, 1, 0)^T, \quad e_4 = (0, 0, 0, 1)^T.$$

Define four nonzero real vectors

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 &= \left(0, 1, -\frac{5}{6}, 1\right)^T, & a_2 &= \left(-\frac{1}{3}, 0, 1, 1\right)^T, \\ a_3 &= (-3, 1, 0, 1)^T, & a_4 &= (1, 1, 1, 0)^T. \end{aligned}$$

Let

$$\psi_i = \frac{a_i}{\|a_i\|} \quad (i = 1, 2, 3, 4),$$

Figure 2: Graphical representation of the explicit counterexample in \mathbb{C}^4 . The orange loop represents the computational-basis context, the blue loop represents the Q -basis context, and dotted edges indicate orthogonality, equivalently state exclusion by the corresponding measurement outcome.

and set

$$S = \{\psi_1, \psi_2, \psi_3, \psi_4\}, \quad T = \{\psi_1, \psi_2, \psi_3\}.$$

The squared norms of the raw vectors are

$$\|a_1\|^2 = \frac{97}{36}, \quad \|a_2\|^2 = \frac{19}{9}, \quad \|a_3\|^2 = 11, \quad \|a_4\|^2 = 3.$$

For all distinct $i, j \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$, one has $\langle \psi_i, \psi_j \rangle \neq 0$. Indeed, direct calculation gives

$\langle a_i, a_j \rangle$	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4
a_1	$\frac{97}{36}$	$\frac{1}{6}$	2	$\frac{1}{6}$
a_2	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{19}{9}$	2	$\frac{2}{3}$
a_3	2	2	11	-2
a_4	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{2}{3}$	-2	3

Consider the rank-one PVM associated with the computational basis,

$$\mathcal{E} = \{|e_1\rangle\langle e_1|, |e_2\rangle\langle e_2|, |e_3\rangle\langle e_3|, |e_4\rangle\langle e_4|\}.$$

The r th outcome excludes ψ_i exactly when $\langle e_r, \psi_i \rangle = 0$. This is equivalent to $\langle e_r, a_i \rangle = 0$, which is just the statement that the r th coordinate of a_i is zero.

The coordinates of the four raw vectors are

	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4
e_1	0	$-\frac{1}{3}$	-3	1
e_2	1	0	1	1
e_3	$-\frac{5}{6}$	1	0	1
e_4	1	1	1	0

Therefore every measurement outcome excludes at least one state, and for each state there is an outcome excluding that state and no other state in S . By Definition 3, S is strongly antidistinguishable.

We now show that $T = \{\psi_1, \psi_2, \psi_3\}$ is weakly antidistinguishable by a second rank-one PVM. Let

$$Q = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{3} & -\frac{6}{7} & -\frac{8}{21} & \frac{2}{21} \\ -\frac{2}{3} & \frac{3}{7} & -\frac{10}{21} & -\frac{8}{21} \\ 0 & -\frac{2}{7} & \frac{3}{7} & -\frac{6}{7} \\ \frac{2}{3} & 0 & -\frac{2}{3} & -\frac{1}{3} \end{pmatrix},$$

and let q_1, q_2, q_3, q_4 be the four columns of Q . The vectors q_1, q_2, q_3, q_4 form an orthonormal basis of \mathbb{C}^4 , so

$$\mathcal{Q} = \{|q_1\rangle\langle q_1|, |q_2\rangle\langle q_2|, |q_3\rangle\langle q_3|, |q_4\rangle\langle q_4|\}$$

is a rank-one PVM.

To see which states are excluded by its outcomes, it is enough to compute $\langle q_r, a_i \rangle$ for $i = 1, 2, 3$. Direct calculation gives

	a_1	a_2	a_3
q_1	0	$\frac{7}{9}$	1
q_2	$\frac{2}{3}$	0	3
q_3	$-\frac{3}{2}$	$-\frac{1}{9}$	0
q_4	0	$-\frac{11}{9}$	-1

Therefore $|q_1\rangle\langle q_1|$ excludes ψ_1 , $|q_2\rangle\langle q_2|$ excludes ψ_2 , $|q_3\rangle\langle q_3|$ excludes ψ_3 , and $|q_4\rangle\langle q_4|$ excludes ψ_1 . Every outcome of \mathcal{Q} excludes at least one state in T .

The Q -basis measurement is the concrete output of Lemma 1 for the triple $x_1 = a_1, x_2 = a_2, x_3 = a_3$, with the hidden plane being $W = \text{span}\{q_2, q_3\}$, its orthogonal complement being $W^\perp = \text{span}\{q_1, q_4\}$, and its projection being $\Pi_W = |q_2\rangle\langle q_2| + |q_3\rangle\langle q_3|$, since $a_1 = \frac{2}{3}q_2 - \frac{3}{2}q_3 \in W$, $\Pi_W a_2 = -\frac{1}{9}q_3 \neq 0$, $\Pi_W a_3 = 3q_2 \neq 0$, and $\langle \Pi_W a_2, \Pi_W a_3 \rangle = 0$. Thus the auxiliary vectors are $u_2 = \Pi_W x_2 = -\frac{1}{9}q_3$, $u_3 = \Pi_W x_3 = 3q_2$, and the two vectors spanning W^\perp are q_1, q_4 . Consequently Proposition 1 implies that S is strongly antidistinguishable by \mathcal{E} , while Lemma 1 supplies the subset measurement proving that $T \subsetneq S$ is weakly antidistinguishable by \mathcal{Q} , so Theorem 1 makes T contextual and Proposition 1 then yields that S is not maximally contextual.

5 Minimality of the counterexample

Our counterexample has four states and lives in \mathbb{C}^4 . We now show that both numbers are forced: no counterexample to the converse can have fewer than four states, and no such counterexample can occur in dimension smaller than 4.

Lemma 2. *Let T be a nonempty finite non-orthogonal set of pure states in \mathbb{C}^d with $|T| \leq 2$. Then T is not weakly antidistinguishable, hence noncontextual.*

Proof. First suppose $T = \{\psi\}$. If a PVM $\{E_1, \dots, E_m\}$ weakly antidistinguished T , then every outcome would have to exclude ψ . Hence $E_k \psi = 0$ for every k , and therefore

$$\psi = I_d \psi = \sum_{k=1}^m E_k \psi = 0,$$

contradicting that ψ is a pure state.

Now suppose $T = \{\psi, \phi\}$ with $\langle \psi, \phi \rangle \neq 0$. Assume, for a contradiction, that a PVM $\{E_1, \dots, E_m\}$ weakly antidistinguishes T . For each outcome E_k , weak antidistinguishability says that $E_k\psi = 0$ or $E_k\phi = 0$. Define

$$A = \{k : E_k\psi = 0\}, \quad B = \{k : E_k\phi = 0\}.$$

Then $A \cup B = \{1, \dots, m\}$. The ranges of the projections E_k are mutually orthogonal and their direct sum is \mathbb{C}^d . Since

$$\psi = \sum_{k=1}^m E_k\psi = \sum_{k \notin A} E_k\psi,$$

we have

$$\psi \in \bigoplus_{k \notin A} \text{ran } E_k.$$

Similarly,

$$\phi \in \bigoplus_{k \notin B} \text{ran } E_k.$$

But $A \cup B = \{1, \dots, m\}$ implies

$$\{k : k \notin A\} \cap \{k : k \notin B\} = \emptyset.$$

The two direct sums above are therefore orthogonal subspaces. Hence $\langle \psi, \phi \rangle = 0$, contradicting the assumption that ψ and ϕ are not orthogonal. Thus no such PVM exists.

By Theorem 1, T is noncontextual. □

Theorem 2 (Cardinality minimality). *Let S be a nonempty finite non-orthogonal set of pure states in \mathbb{C}^d . If S is strongly antidistinguishable and $|S| \leq 3$, then S is maximally contextual. Consequently, no counterexample can have fewer than four states.*

Proof. Since strong antidistinguishability implies weak antidistinguishability, Lemma 2 shows that the cases $|S| = 1$ and $|S| = 2$ cannot occur. Hence, under the hypotheses, we must have $|S| = 3$.

Since S is strongly antidistinguishable, it is weakly antidistinguishable by Definition 3. Since S is non-orthogonal, Theorem 1 implies that S is contextual.

Let $T \subsetneq S$ be a proper subset. Because $|S| = 3$, we have $|T| \leq 2$. If $|T| = 2$, then the two states in T are not orthogonal because S is non-orthogonal. Hence Lemma 2 implies that T is not contextual. Thus no proper subset of S is contextual. Therefore S is maximally contextual. □

Theorem 3 (Dimension minimality). *No counterexample exists in \mathbb{C}^d for $d < 4$.*

Proof. Let $S = \{\psi_1, \dots, \psi_n\}$ be a nonempty finite non-orthogonal set of pure states in \mathbb{C}^d that is strongly antidistinguishable. We show that if $d < 4$, then S is maximally contextual.

Since strong antidistinguishability implies weak antidistinguishability, Lemma 2 gives $n \geq 3$. Let $\{E_1, \dots, E_m\}$ be a PVM strongly antidistinguishing S . For each $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, choose an outcome $E_{k(i)}$ such that

$$E_{k(i)}\psi_i = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad E_{k(i)}\psi_j \neq 0 \quad \text{for every } j \neq i.$$

If $i \neq j$, then $k(i) \neq k(j)$. Indeed, if $k(i) = k(j)$, then the exclusion condition for ψ_i gives $E_{k(i)}\psi_j \neq 0$, while the exclusion condition for ψ_j gives $E_{k(j)}\psi_j = 0$, a contradiction.

For each i , the projection $E_{k(i)}$ is nonzero, because $n \geq 3$ allows us to choose some $j \neq i$, and then $E_{k(i)}\psi_j \neq 0$. Thus $E_{k(1)}, \dots, E_{k(n)}$ are n distinct nonzero outcomes of the PVM. The ranges of

all outcomes of a PVM are mutually orthogonal and their direct sum is \mathbb{C}^d . Therefore the sum of their ranks is d . In particular,

$$n \leq \sum_{i=1}^n \text{rank } E_{k(i)} \leq \sum_{r=1}^m \text{rank } E_r = d.$$

Hence $n \leq d$. If $d < 4$, then $n \leq 3$. Combining this with $n \geq 3$ gives $n = 3$, and Theorem 2 implies that S is maximally contextual. \square

6 Discussion

Our construction uses two different measurements. The computational-basis measurement certifies strong antidistinguishability of the four-state set S . The Q -basis measurement certifies weak antidistinguishability of a proper subset. The fourth Q -basis outcome is deliberately arranged to exclude ψ_1 again, so the first three states already form a contextual proper subset. This is exactly what maximal contextuality forbids. Consequently, strong antidistinguishability is best understood as a condition about the abundance of exclusion outcomes, rather than as a test for contextual irreducibility. A converse-type criterion would therefore have to rule out hidden weakly antidistinguishable subfamilies.

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